

Systematic review of the efficacy and safety of GLP-1 receptor agonists in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus

Lora Petrova¹, Kalina Andreevska¹, Iva Parvova², Valentina Petkova³

¹ Laboratory of Social Pharmacy, Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Sofia University "Saint Kliment Ohridski", 1, James Bourchier Blvd., Sofia 1164, Bulgaria

² Department of Rheumatology, Medical University of Sofia, 13, Urvich str., Sofia 1612, Bulgaria

³ Department of Organization and Economics of Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, 2, Dunav Str., Sofia 1000, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Valentina Petkova (vpetkova@pharmfac.mu-sofia.bg)

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Abstract

In recent years, incretin mimetics have become an important part of type 2 diabetes mellitus therapy. The aim of this study is to evaluate the efficacy and safety of glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptor agonists. We performed a literature search of scientific publications in MEDLINE and Central Library of Medicine databases by predefined keywords for the period 2004 to 2023 containing information for the efficacy and safety of GLP-1 receptor agonists. The systematic review is in accordance with the PRISMA standard and the PICOS tool. There is strong evidence to support the use of GLP-1 agonists in overweight or obese patients who have cardiovascular disease, impaired renal function or are at high risk of hypoglycaemia. The safety profiles of all representatives of this class are similar. Semaglutide and Tirzepatide demonstrated the highest efficacy in reducing glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) - 1.70% and 2.37%, respectively. We found the superiority of GLP-1 receptor agonists over other antidiabetic medicinal products in terms of HbA1c reduction and weight loss without the risk of hypoglycemic episodes.

Keywords

GLP-1 receptor agonists, diabetes mellitus, efficacy, safety, systematic review

Introduction

Type 2 diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disease with a complex pathogenesis involving a number of factors - impaired insulin secretion, impaired insulin action (insulin resistance), reduced incretin effect, increased glucagon secretion, increased hepatic glucose production, reduced muscle glucose uptake, increased lipolysis, increased glucose reabsorption at kidney level and neurotransmitter dysfunction. Beta-cell dysfunction represents a major defect in the pathogenesis of

type 2 diabetes mellitus. Loss of incretin effect is the cause of the decline in beta-cell function (Tankova 2013). It has been proved that insulin secretion is greater in response to oral glucose intake than to isoglycemic intravenous glucose infusion, a phenomenon called the "incretin effect". Incretins are hormones produced by the intestinal mucosa in response to oral intake of nutrients that enhance glucose-stimulated insulin secretion and lower blood glucose levels. Incretins also reduce insulin secretion when glucose levels are near to normal (Hinnen 2017). The main incretins are glucagon-like

peptide-1 (GLP-1), which is produced by L-cells in the ileum and colon, as well as glucose-dependent insulinotropic polypeptide (GIP), which is secreted by K-cells in the duodenum and jejunum. The incretins undergo the action of an enzyme called dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) after their release and during this process the first two amino acids of the two incretins are cleaved off and converted to inactive peptides. The inactivation process determines the short half-lives of the incretins, about 2 minutes for GLP-1 and about 5 minutes for GIP (Tankova 2013). As the incretin effect is reduced in type 2 diabetes mellitus, two strategies of incretin-based therapy have been developed to overcome the rapid inactivation of incretins and to utilize their antidiabetic effects. One strategy involves the use of GLP-1 receptor agonists, which are divided into two groups - GLP-1 mimetics and long-acting GLP-1 analogues, which are also not a subject of degradation by DPP-4. The second strategy involves the use of GIP receptor agonists. The GLP-1 receptor agonist group includes two subgroups, exendin-based GLP-1 receptor agonists or GLP-1 mimetics (Exenatide, Exenatide extended-release and Lixisenatide) and human GLP-1 backbone analogues (Liraglutide, Albiglutide, Dulaglutide, Semaglutide). Tirzepatide is a GIP analogue, which activates both GLP-1 and GIP receptors. GLP-1 and GIP stimulate the insulin secretion from pancreatic beta-cells. There is an increase in the early phase of secretion as well as a decrease in the proinsulin:insulin ratio, which is a marker of beta-cell function. An important effect of the inhibition of DPP-4 and the subsequent increase in GLP-1 level is the suppression of glucagon secretion. Increased insulin secretion leads to increased glucose uptake by peripheral tissues - muscles and adipose tissue. Decreased glucagon secretion and the increased insulin secretion leads to decreased endogenous hepatic glucose production. Intravenous administration of exogenous GLP-1 in patients with type 2 diabetes has been shown to reduce plasma glucose concentrations to normal fasting values, even in patients who have had an inadequate response to oral glucose-lowering agents. The effects of exogenous GLP-1 observed after its administration to patients with type 2 diabetes include: decreased glucagon concentrations, improved insulin sensitivity, decreased HbA1c levels, delayed gastric emptying, increased feelings of satiety, decreased free fatty acid concentrations and decreased body weight (Hinnen 2017). GLP-1 mimetics are synthetic analogues of exendin-4, a peptide naturally secreted in saliva and concentrated in the tail of the giant Gila lizard. Exenatide and Lixisenatide stimulate insulin secretion by the beta-cells of the pancreas in response to food intake in a glucose-dependent manner - a greater amount of insulin is released, which helps to lower postprandial blood glucose. The response of the pancreas to secrete insulin decreases as the blood glucose level decreases to normal values. Exenatide and Lixisenatide suppress glucagon secretion which is increased in type 2 diabetes mellitus, hence decreases hepatic glucose production. They also reduce the rate at which glucose from ingested food reaches the circulation by slowing gastric emptying. GLP-1 mimetics have a prolonged effect on reducing appetite by inducing a feeling of satiety by binding to receptors in the hypothalamus. GLP-1 analogues are structural analogues of human

glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1). Liraglutide is an analogue of GLP-1 with a 97% degree of homology to human GLP-1 that binds to and activates the GLP-1 receptor. Unlike natural GLP-1, the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic profile of Liraglutide in humans make it suitable for administration once-daily. When administered subcutaneously, the prolonged action profile is based on three mechanisms: self-association leading to delayed absorption; binding to albumin; greater enzymatic stability relative to enzymes DPP-4 and neutral endopeptidase (NEP), resulting in a long plasma half-life (EMA 2009). Semaglutide is a GLP-1 analogue with a 94% degree of homology to human GLP-1. Semaglutide acts as a GLP-1 receptor agonist that selectively binds to and activates the GLP-1 receptor targeting native GLP-1. The effects on glucose and appetite are specifically mediated through GLP-1 receptors in the pancreas and brain. Semaglutide lowers blood glucose in a glucose-dependent manner by stimulating insulin secretion and reducing glucagon secretion in high blood glucose levels. The mechanism of lowering blood glucose also involves delaying gastric emptying in the early postprandial phase. In hypoglycemia, Semaglutide reduces insulin secretion and does not impair glucagon secretion. A once-weekly subcutaneous formulation of Semaglutide has been developed as well as an oral formulation (EMA 2018). Albiglutide is a GLP-1 dimer that is bound to human albumin resistant to the action of DPP-4 (Tankova 2013). Its marketing authorisation has been terminated at the request of the marketing authorisation holder (MAH). Dulaglutide is a long-acting agonist of the human GLP-1 receptor. Its molecule consists of 2 identical disulfide-linked chains, each containing a modified human GLP-1 analog sequence covalently linked to a modified human immunoglobulin G4 (IgG4) heavy chain fragment (Fc) with a small peptide bond. The GLP-1 analog moiety of Dulaglutide is approximately 90% homologous to natural human GLP-1. Unlike natural GLP-1, Dulaglutide is resistant to degradation by DPP-4 and has a large size, which delays absorption and lowers renal clearance (EMA 2014). Tirzepatide is a long-acting GLP-1 and GIP-receptor agonist, and its activity toward the GIP receptor is similar to native GIP, whereas its activity toward GLP-1 is lower compared to the native GLP-1 receptor. Both receptors are present on α and β endocrine cells of the pancreas, heart, immune cells (leukocytes), intestine and kidneys (EMA 2024). According to the American Diabetes Association (ADA) guidelines of 2023, GLP-1 receptor agonists are recommended to reduce cardiovascular risk. They not only reduce the risk of cardiovascular events and hypoglycemia, but also demonstrate the potential to reduce the progression of chronic kidney disease (CKD). GLP-1 agonists are recommended for patients with a history of myocardial infarction and stroke. GLP-1 agonists with proven cardiovascular benefits include Liraglutide, subcutaneous Semaglutide, Dulaglutide (ElSayed et al. 2023). GLP-1 agonists are usually administered subcutaneously due to their poor oral bioavailability (Table 1). Liraglutide is injected daily. Dosing of Dulaglutide and Semaglutide is weekly, and Exenatide can be dosed twice daily or once weekly. The oral form of Semaglutide is taken daily. Tirzepatide is administered weekly (Collins et al. 2024).

Table 1. Doses and dose ranges of GLP-1 receptor agonists.

INN	Dose range	Dose
Exenatide BID	2× daily	5 µg and 10 µg subcutaneously twice a day
Exenatide QW	1× weekly	2 mg subcutaneously once a week
Liraglutide	1× daily	0,6, 1,2 mg and 1,8 mg subcutaneously once a day
Lixisenatide	1× daily	10 µg and 20 µg subcutaneously once a day
Dulaglutide	1× weekly	0,75 mg and 1,5 mg subcutaneously once a week
Semaglutide s.c.	1× weekly	0,25 mg, 0,5 mg and 1 mg once a week
Semaglutide p.o.	1× daily	3 mg, 7 mg and 14 mg once a day
Tirzepatide	1× weekly	2,5 mg, 5 mg, 10 mg and 15 mg once a week

The aim of this study is to perform a retrospective systematic review of scientific publications evaluating the efficacy and safety of GLP-1 receptor agonists in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. The primary endpoints assessed are change in glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) level from baseline, effect of the investigational medicinal product on body weight, as well as the occurrence of adverse events during clinical trials.

Materials and methods

The systematic review is conducted in accordance with the recommendations of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines (Fig. 1) (Moher et al. 2009). PRISMA is an evidence-based minimum set of items for reporting in systematic reviews and meta-analyses (Shamseer et al. 2015). The study protocol is developed in accordance with the PRISMA 2009 Checklist, and for this purpose we

predefined: study topic, design, search strategy, inclusion and exclusion criteria, methods of data collection and analysis (Hutton et al. 2015). PRISMA 2009 is developed primarily for systematic reviews of studies that evaluate the effects of health interventions, regardless of the design of the included studies. Study design: retrospective observational study. Search strategy - We performed the review of scientific publications in English using the following keywords: diabetes mellitus type 2, GLP-1 receptor agonists, efficacy, safety, clinical trial, HbA1c. Study period: The search of scientific publications is conducted in MEDLINE, Central Library of Medicine and refereed scientific journals databases for the period January 2004 to December 2023. Over a period of 19 years, we found 276 scientific publications. The following data were extracted: first author's surname, year of publication, clinical trial, trial design and duration, study population, demographics, duration of diabetes, previous glucose-lowering therapy, baseline glycated hemoglobin level before initiation of the clinical trial, primary end points, efficacy data (Figs 2, 3), and adverse events occurring during the clinical trial (Table 6). Two of the authors independently of each other extracted data from the research articles that were determined to meet the inclusion criteria.

Results

The selection of the analyzed scientific articles, performed according to the search strategy, is presented as a PRISMA flow diagram (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Overview of PRISMA flow - diagram.

Figure 2. Relative proportions of HbA1c reduction for different types of GLP-1 receptor agonists.

Figure 3. Comparison between GLP-1 receptor agonists in terms of weight reduction.

The literature search is limited to articles published in English and Bulgarian. In the initial search were found 276 scientific publications. We screened 276 abstracts and performed a search for the full texts of the articles. We excluded 200 articles because the abstract did not contain the keywords: diabetes mellitus type 2, GLP-1 receptor agonists, Exenatide, Liraglutide, Lixisenatide, Dulaglutide, Semaglutide, Tirzepatide. At the final stage, we excluded 30 full-text articles from the remaining 76 articles because they did not contain clinical trial, efficacy, safety or glycated hemoglobin data.

We retained for analysis 46 scientific publications that met our original inclusion criteria and reviewed clinical trials evaluating the efficacy and safety of GLP-1 receptor agonists (Table 2).

Table 2. Total number of analysed articles by INN.

INN	Number of studies (n-46)	Total (%)
Exenatide - 2x daily	3	6.52%
Exenatide - once weekly	7	15.21%
Liraglutide	7	15.21%
Lixisenatide	5	10.87%
Dulaglutide	8	17.39%
Semaglutide-s.c.	6	13.04%
Semaglutide- p.o.	5	10.87%
Tirzepatide	5	10.87%

We used the PICOS - Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcomes, Study design (Methley et al. 2014) to assess the results (Tables 3–5). The PICO analysis includes 4 potential health components - trial population data, intervention applied, comparison product, and outcome assessment. It has been adopted by the Cochrane Collaboration (Higgins et al. 2013). In the modified version, PICOS “S” refers to the study design. Adverse events occurring during clinical trials are presented according to the MedDRA system-organ classification (MedDRA SOC), version 24.1 and the general terminology criteria for adverse events (MedDRA 2022). The results of differential PICOS analysis by GLP-1 receptor agonist type are presented in tabular form (Tables 3–5) by group as follows:

Exenidin-based GLP-1 receptor agonists have been represented in 15 clinical trials, of which 6 were placebo-controlled, 6 were active-controlled and 3 were placebo and active-controlled. Their duration was between 26–52 weeks and all were randomized controlled. The total number of patients was 7411, of which 908 patients were on therapy with Exenatide 5 µg and 10 µg, 3684 patients were on Exenatide 2 mg and 2819 patients were on Lixisenatide 20 µg. The interventions administered were: Exenatide subcutaneously twice daily 5 and 10 µg,

Table 3. PICOS - Exenadin-based GLP-1 receptor agonists.

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, Weight reduction)	Outcomes safety (Adverse events rated by MedRA SOC)	Study design
N=165 with or without Metformin. HbA1c $\geq 7.1\%$ and $\leq 10.0\%$ (Liutkus et al. 2010)	Exenatide 5 and 10 μg twice daily	Placebo	Mean reduction in HbA1c level by -0.84%. Reduction of body weight by -1.4 kg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 12%, vomiting - 8%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: mild hypoglycaemia in 4% of patients. Nervous system disorders: headache - 4%.	26-week multicenter, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial
N=377 on therapy with maximum dose of sulfonylurea. HbA1c 8.6% +/- 1.2% (Buse et al. 2004)	4 weeks with 5 μg of subcutaneous Exenatide twice daily (arm A and B). Subsequently, in arm B, the dose was increased to 10 μg of Exenatide twice a day.	Placebo	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -0.86% and -0.46% with 10 μg and 5 μg Exenatide. Dose-dependent weight reduction of 10 μg by -1.6 kg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea - 5% in the arm of 10- μg Exenatide, 6% in the arm of 5- μg Exenatide. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: mild to moderate hypoglycaemia up to 36% in the 10- μg Exenatide arm, 14% in the 5- μg Exenatide arm. Presence of anti-Exenatide antibodies (41%)	30-week randomized, triple-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel-group clinical trial
N= 366 with poor glycemic control, on therapy with maximum doses of Metformin. HbA1c 7.1– 11.0%. (DeFronzo et al. 2005)	5 μg of Exenatide subcutaneously twice daily for 4 weeks, followed by 5 or 10 μg of Exenatide for 26 weeks, with Metformin.	Placebo	Mean reduction in HbA1c level by -0.78% with 10 μg , and -0.40% with 5 μg of Exenatide. Dose-dependent weight reduction of -2.8 kg by 10 μg -1.6 kg with 5 μg Exenatide.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 3.5% and 2.7% in the shoulders of 10- μg and 5- μg Exenatide. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: mild to moderate hypoglycaemia 5.3% in the arm of 10- μg Exenatide, 4.5% in the arm of 5- μg Exenatide. Presence of anti-Exenatide antibodies 43%.	30-week randomized, triple-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel-group clinical trial
N=375 treated only with diet and exercise or on therapy with Metformin, sulfonylurea, Pioglitazone. HbA1c 8.5% (Wysham et al.2018)	Exenatide QWS-AI (2 mg)	Exenatide twice daily (10 μg)	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.4% with Exenatide QWS-AI 2 mg. Weight reduction by -1.49 kg with Exenatide QWS- AI.	Gastrointestinal disorders: in 22.7% of participants taking Exenatide QWS-AI (2 mg), of which: nausea 9.6%, diarrhoea 5.2%, vomiting 3.5%, acute pancreatitis – reported in 1 patient. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: mild hypoglycaemia when used with sulfonylurea. Nervous system disorders: headache 5.7%. General disorders and administration site conditions: injection site reactions 26.6%. Anti-Exenatide antibodies in 28.8% of patients.	28-week, randomized, open-label, active-controlled clinical trial
N=365 on Metformin therapy. HbA1c 7.1% up to 11.0% (Gadde et al. 2017)	Exenatide QWS-AI 2.0 mg	Sitagliptin 100 mg once a day or oral placebo.	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.13% with Exenatide QWS-AI 2.0 mg. Weight reduction with -1.12 kg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 8.8%, vomiting 3.3%, diarrhoea 2.8%. Infections and infestations: nasopharyngitis at 0.6% of the patients. General disorders and effects at the injection site: injection site reactions 18.8%. Anti-Exenatide antibodies were present in 63.3% of patients.	28-week, randomized, active and placebo- controlled, multicenter clinical trial
N=427 with poor glycemic control with oral antidiabetic medicinal products. HbA1c 8.5% (Inagaki et al. 2012)	Exenatide QW 2 mg	Insulin glargine	Target HbA1c levels of $\leq 7.0\%$ were achieved by 42.2% of patients. Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.11% with Exenatide QW 2 mg. Weight reduction by -2.01 kg.	Gastrointestinal disorders – nausea 12.6%, vomiting 8.4%, diarrhoea 8.8%, constipation – 11.2%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: Exenatide QW 2 mg is associated with a lower risk of hypoglycaemia – 0.5% compared to Insulin glargine. General disorders and administration site conditions: injection site reactions - 40.9%. Infections and infestations: nasopharyngitis - 25.6%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: decreased appetite 5.1%.	26-week, randomized, open-label, parallel-group, multicenter, non-inferiority clinical trial
N=295, who were naive to drug therapy, or on one or more oral antidiabetic agents. HbA1c 8.3%, (Buse et al. 2010)	Exenatide 2 mg with prolonged release, administered once a week	10 μg of Exenatide administered twice daily	Mean reduction of HbA1c by -1.9% with Exenatide 2 mg. Weight reduction by -4.1 kg.	Gastrointestinal disorders – diarrhoea 8.6%, nausea 7%, vomiting 6.3%. Infections and infestations: nasopharyngitis 7.8%, upper respiratory tract infections 12.5%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: hypoglycaemia 9% when used with sulfonylurea.	52-week, randomized, non- inferiority clinical trial
N=491 on Metformin therapy. HbA1c 8.5%. (Bergental et al. 2010)	Exenatide 2 mg once a week with an oral placebo once a day	100 mg oral Sitagliptin once a day plus an injectable placebo once a week; or 45 mg oral Pioglitazone once daily plus an injectable placebo once a week.	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.5% with Exenatide 2 mg. Weight reduction by -2.3 kg with Exenatide 2 mg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 24%, diarrhoea 18%, vomiting 11%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: severe hypoglycaemia 1%. Nervous system disorders: headache 9%. Infections and infestations: upper respiratory tract infections - 4%. General disorders and administration site conditions: injection site reactions 5%.	26-week randomized, double-blind clinical trial

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, Weight reduction)	Outcomes safety (Adverse events rated by MedRA SOC)	Study design
N=820, who have not been on pharmacological therapy so far. HbA1c 8.5% (Russell-Jones et al. 2011)	Subcutaneous Exenatide 2 mg + oral placebo (n = 248)	Metformin 2000 mg/day + subcutaneous (s.c.) placebo (n = 246), Pioglitazone 45 mg/day + s.c. placebo (n = 163), or Sitagliptin 100 mg/day + s.c. placebo (n = 163)	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.53% with Exenatide 2 mg. Weight reduction by -2 kg with Exenatide 2 mg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 11.3% and diarrhoea 10.9%. Nervous system disorders: headache 8.1%. Infections and infestations: nasopharyngitis - 7.7%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: mild hypoglycemia 2%. Nodules at the injection site had 10.5%. Anti-Exenatide antibodies had 43.1%.	26-week, randomized, double-blind clinical trial
N=911, taking 1 or more glucose-lowering medicinal products. HbA1c 7.1% - 11, 0% (Buse et al. 2012)	Exenatide 2 mg once a week	Liraglutide 1.8 mg once a day	The mean reduction in HbA1c level is by -1.28% with Exenatide 2 mg Weight reduction by -2.68 kg with Exenatide 2 mg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 9%, diarrhoea 6%, vomiting 4%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: decreased appetite 4%. Nervous system disorders: headache 6%. Infections and infestations: nasopharyngitis 7%. Nodules at the injection site had 10% of patients.	26-week, open-label, randomized, parallel-group clinical trial
N=639 with poor glycemic control with Metformin. HbA1c 7-10%. (Rosenstock et al. 2013)	Lixisenatide 20 µg once daily (n=318)	Exenatide 10 µg twice daily (n=316)	Mean reduction of HbA1c level of -0.79% with administration of Lixisenatide 20 µg Weight reduction by -2.96 kg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 24.5%, vomiting 10.1% and diarrhoea 10.4%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: symptomatic hypoglycaemia: 2.5% with Lixisenatide 20 µg versus 7.9% with Exenatide 10 µg.	24-week randomized, parallel-group, multicenter clinical trial
N=495 on basal insulin therapy, but poor glycemic control. HbA1c 8.4% (Riddle et al. 2013)	Lixisenatide 20 µg to basal insulin. The dose of basal insulin remains unchanged - 55 U/day.	Placebo	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -0.7% with Lixisenatide 20 µg. Weight reduction by -1.8 kg with Lixisenatide 20 µg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 26.2%, vomiting 8.2%, diarrhoea 7.3%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: symptomatic hypoglycaemia 26.5%. 70% of participants were positive for anti-Lixisenatide antibodies.	24-week randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel-group clinical trial.
N=680 with poor glycemic control with Metformin. HbA1c 7-10%. (Ahrén et al. 2013)	Lixisenatide 20 µg once a day, administered before morning or evening meals as an adjunctive therapy to Metformin.	Placebo administered in the morning or evening.	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -0.8 -0.9% with Lixisenatide 20 µg, administered in the morning or evening. Weight reduction by -2 kg.	Adverse events were experienced by 69.4% of patients. Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 22.7% and 21.2%, vomiting 9.4% and 13.3% for Lixisenatide 20 µg administered in the morning and in the evening, diarrhoea 10.6%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: symptomatic hypoglycaemia in 2.4% and 5.1% with Lixisenatide 20 µg administered in the morning and evening.	24-week, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel-group, multicenter clinical trial.
N=521 with poor glycemic control, on therapy with oral antidiabetic medicinal products. HbA1c ≥7.5% up to ≤9.5%. (Terauchi et al. 2020)	Combination with a fixed ratio of Insulin glargine/ Lixisenatide (iGlarLixi)	Insulin glargine U100 (iGlar)	The reduction in HbA1c level is significantly greater with the combined product iGlarLixi by an average of -1.40%. Weight gain of 0.26 kg with iGlarLixi.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: symptomatic hypoglycaemia was reported in 14.2% of patients with iGlarLixi and 12.3% with iGlar. No severe hypoglycaemia has been reported. Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 9.6% of iGlarLixi patients. Infections and infestations: nasopharyngitis was reported by 18.8% on therapy with iGlarLixi.	26-week multicenter, open-label, randomized, parallel-group clinical trial.
N=484 with poor glycemic control, on therapy only with Metformin, HbA1c 7-10%. (Bolli et al. 2013)	Single- and two-stage dose increase of Lixisenatide up to 20 µg once daily	Placebo	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -0.8-0.9% with administration of Lixisenatide 20 µg. Reduction of body weight by -2.7 kg with Lixisenatide 20 µg.	Adverse events were reported by 67.7%, 70.8% of participants treated with Lixisenatide with a single/two-stage dose increase. Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 26.1-35.4%, vomiting 11.8-15.5%, diarrhoea 6.2-12.4%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: symptomatic hypoglycaemia 1.9 and 2.5% with Lixisenatide 20 µg, no severe episodes.	24-week randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel-group, multicenter clinical trial.

Exenatide 2 mg administered once weekly and Lixisenatide 20 µg once daily. Exenatide 5 and 10 µg twice daily in the three clinical trials analysed was compared with placebo only. Exenatide 2 mg administered once weekly was compared with placebo and with Exenatide 10 µg, with Sitagliptin 100 mg once daily, Insulin glargine, with Pioglitazone 45 mg once daily, Metformin 2000 mg/day and with Liraglutide 1.8 mg. Lixisenatide 20 µg once daily was compared in three clinical trials with placebo, and in active-controlled trials was compared with Exenatide

10 µg twice daily. The Insulin glargine/ Lixisenatide combination product was compared in one clinical trial to Insulin glargine.

The results on efficacy in reducing HbA1c show that the most significant reduction of -1.41% is observed with Exenatide 2 mg, while the mean reduction is -1% with Lixisenatide 20 µg and -0.83% with Exenatide 5 and 10 µg. We calculated that the body weight reduction with Lixisenatide 20 µg is 2.34 kg, with Exenatide 2 mg is 2.18 kg, and with Exenatide 5 and 10 µg is 1.93 kg.

Table 4. PICOS for human GLP-1 analogues.

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, Weight reduction)	Outcomes safety (Adverse events rated by MedRA SOC)	Study design
N=533 on previous therapy with an oral antidiabetic drug. HbA1c 7–11%. (Zinman et al. 2009)	Liraglutide once a day (1.2 or 1.8 mg) in combination with Metformin (1 g twice a day) and Rosiglitazone (4 mg twice a day).	Placebo in combination with Metformin (1 g twice daily) and Rosiglitazone (4 mg twice daily).	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.5% Reduction of body weight by an average of -1.0 and -2.0 kg with Liraglutide 1.2 mg and 1.8 mg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea - 29% and 40%, vomiting 7% and 17% with 1.2 mg and 1.8 mg Liraglutide. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: mild hypoglycaemia in 9.0% and 7.9% of patients. Peripheral edema - 5.1% and 1.7% with 1.2 mg and 1.8 mg of Liraglutide.	26-week, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel-group clinical trial.
N=1091 on oral antidiabetic therapy. HbA1c 7–11%. (Nauck et al. 2008)	Liraglutide (0.6, 1.2 or 1.8 mg/day, injected subcutaneously) + Metformin 1 g 2x daily	Placebo or Glimepiride 4 mg + Metformin 1 g 2x daily	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.0% with 1.8 mg Liraglutide. Average weight reduction by -2.8 kg. Significant decrease in systolic pressure by 2-3 mmHg with 1.2 and 1.8 mg Liraglutide.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: mild hypoglycaemia (approximately 3%) is comparable to that of placebo, but less than that of Glimepiride (17%). Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea - 11-19%, vomiting - 5–7%, and diarrhoea - 10-15%, one case of acute pancreatitis was reported. Investigations: no significant differences in calcitonin were found between the Liraglutide and placebo groups.	26-week randomized, double-blind, placebo- and actively controlled, parallel-group clinical trial.
N=1041 all on therapy with Glimepiride. HbA1c 8.4 +/- 1.0%. (Marre et al. 2009)	Combination therapy of Liraglutide (0.6, 1.2 or 1.8 mg/day) with Glimepiride (2-4 mg/day)	Rosiglitazone 4 mg/day or placebo with Glimepiride (2-4 mg/day)	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.1% c 1,8 mg Liraglutide. Weight reduction by -0.2 kg with Liraglutide 1.8 mg.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: minor hypoglycaemia (< 10%), Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea (< 11%), vomiting (< 5%) and diarrhoea (< 8%). Anti-Liraglutide antibodies were found in 9-13% of patients.	26-week, randomized, double-blind clinical trial.
N=746 only on diet and exercise or on therapy with an oral antidiabetic medicinal product. HbA1c 7–11%. (Garber et al. 2008)	Liraglutide 1,2 mg or 1,8 mg	Glimepiride 8 mg	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by an average of -0.84% and -1.14% with Liraglutide 1.2 and 1.8 mg, respectively. Weight reduction by about -2 kg. Reduction of systolic pressure by 2.1–3.6 mm Hg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea - 10%, vomiting 9–12.4%, diarrhoea -15.5-18.7%. In two participants was reported acute pancreatitis. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: mild hypoglycaemia - 8-12%.	52-week randomized, double-blind, parallel-group, active - controlled clinical trial
N=464 at maximum tolerable doses of Metformin, sulfonylurea or both. HbA1c 8.2%. (Buse et al. 2009)	Liraglutide 1,8 mg once a day	Exenatide 10 µg twice a day	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1,12% with 1,8 mg Liraglutide. Weight reduction by -3.24 kg. Reduction of systolic and diastolic pressure by 2.51 and 1.05 mmHg, respectively. LDL decreased by -0.44 mmol/L, and total cholesterol by -0.20 mmol/L.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: minor hypoglycaemia is less common with Liraglutide and Exenatide (25.5% vs. 33.6%). Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 25.5%, vomiting 6%, diarrhoea 12.3%. Infections and infections: nasopharyngitis 11.5%. Investigations: At baseline, the mean calcitonin values were lower than 1 ng/l, below the upper limit of the reference value for both women (5.0 ng/l) and men (8.4 ng/l).	26-week randomized, multinational (15 countries), parallel - group clinical trial
N=303 taking a stable dose of SGLT2i (Sodium-glucose Cotransporter-2 Inhibitor) ± Metformin. HbA1c 7.0%- 9.5% (Blonde et al. 2020)	Liraglutide 1,8 mg/day, added to SGLT2i ± Metformin.	Placebo added to SGLT2i ± Metformin.	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -0.98% with 1.8 mg Liraglutide. Reduction of body weight by -2.81 kg.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: mild hypoglycaemia was experienced by 8.9%. Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea - 26.2%, diarrhoea 9.4%, vomiting 8.4%. Investigations: increased lipase 1%.	26-week randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind, multinational clinical trial.
N=1663 treated with Metformin with or without Pioglitazone. HbA1c 8,3%. (Gough et al. 2014)	Daily injections of IDegLira (Insulin degludec/ Liraglutide)	Insulin degludec or Liraglutide 1,8 mg / day.	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.9% to 6.4%. Weight reduction by -0.5 kg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 8.8% vs. 19.7% for IDegLira vs. Liraglutide 1.8 mg, diarrhoea 8% and vomiting 4%. Nervous system disorders: headache - 11%. Investigations: increased lipase - 5%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: hypoglycaemia was 1.8% with IDegLira.	26-week randomized, parallel-group clinical trial
N=737 with poor glycemic control. HbA1c 7.0–10.5%. (Chen et al. 2018)	Administration of Dulaglutide 1.5 and 0.75 mg once a week	Glimepiride 1–3 mg/ day	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.48% with 1.5 mg and by -1,22% with 0,75 mg Dulaglutide. Weight reduction by -1.46 kg and by -0.77 kg with 1.5 and 0.75 mg Dulaglutide.	Gastrointestinal disorders: diarrhoea 6.7%, nausea 4.2%, vomiting 2.7% and bloating. Investigations: increased lipase. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: decreased appetite, mild hypoglycemia - 8.3%	26-week multinational, multicenter, double-blind, randomized, parallel-arm clinical trial.
N=300 on monotherapy with Glimepiride. HbA1c 8.4%. (Dungan et al. 2016)	Dulaglutide 1,5 mg once a week	Placebo	Mean reduction of HbA1c by -1.4%. Reduction of body weight by -0.91 kg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 10.5%, diarrhoea 8.4% and belching 5.9%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: total hypoglycaemia was higher with Dulaglutide 1.5 mg - 20.9% compared to placebo.	24-week randomized, double-blind, placebo- controlled clinical trial

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, Weight reduction)	Outcomes safety (Adverse events rated by MedRA SOC)	Study design
N=361, receiving sulfonylurea and/or biguanides. HbA1c 7.0–10.0% (Araki et al. 2015)	Dulaglutide 0,75 mg once a week	Insulin glargine once a day	Mean reduction of HbA1c level is by -1,44%. Reduction of body weight by -1,42 kg.	Infections and infestations: nasopharyngitis 27%. Gastrointestinal disorders: diarrhoea 12%, nausea 9%, constipation 9%, vomiting 5%. Investigations: increased lipase 5%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: hypoglycaemia was 26% with Dulaglutide compared to 48% Insulin glargine.	26-week, randomized, open-label, parallel- group, multicenter clinical trial
N=810 taking Metformin or Glimepiride. HbA1c 8.1 ± 1.0% (Giorgino et al. 2015)	Dulaglutide 1,5 mg and Dulaglutide 0,75 mg	Insulin glargine	Mean reduction in HbA1c level was - 1.08% with 1.5 mg Dulaglutide, with - 0.76% with 0.75 mg Dulaglutide. Weight reduction by - 1.87 and - 1.33 kg c 1.5 and 0.75 mg Dulaglutide.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: hypoglycemia was lower with Dulaglutide - 55.3–54.4% compared to 69.1% with Insulin glargine. Investigations: increased amylase and lipase. Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea (15.4% and 7.7%), diarrhoea (10.6% and 9.2%), two cases of acute pancreatitis with 1.5 mg Dulaglutide and one with 0.75 mg Dulaglutide. Infections and infestations: nasopharyngitis 5.5% and 4.4% with 1.5 mg and 0.75 mg Dulaglutide.	78-week double-blind, randomized, multicenter clinical trial
N=976 on Metformin (1500-3000 mg) and Pioglitazone (30-45 mg) therapy. HbA1c 8.1%. (Wysham et al. 2014)	Dulaglutide 1,5 mg and Dulaglutide 0,75 mg,	Exenatide 10 µg or placebo.	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by - 1.51% and -1.30% with 1.5 mg and 0.75 mg Dulaglutide. Reduction of body weight by -1,30 kg with 1,5 mg Dulaglutide.	Metabolism and nutrition disorders: hypoglycaemia is lower with Dulaglutide 1.5 mg about 10% than 16% with Exenatide. Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 16-28%, vomiting 6–17% and diarrhoea 8-11%. Infections and infestations: Nasopharyngitis - 7%. Investigations: a slight increase in amylase and lipase.	52-week, multicenter, randomized, parallel-group clinical trial
N=807 treated only with diet and exercise or on monotherapy with a low dose of oral antidiabetic medicinal product for no more than 3 months. HbA1c ≥6.5% and ≤9.5%. (Umpierrez et al. 2014)	Dulaglutide 1.5 mg and 0.75 mg/week	Metformin 2000 mg/day	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by - 0.78% and - 0.71% with Dulaglutide 1.5 and 0.75 mg. Reduction of body weight by - 2.29 and - 1.36 kg. Systolic and diastolic pressure decreased by -2.7 and -1.4 mmHg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea - 19.7% and 11.5%, diarrhoea 11.2% and 7.8%, and vomiting 9.7% and 7.4% with 1.5 mg and 0.75 mg Dulaglutide. Infections and infestations: nasopharyngitis 3.0-5.2%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: mild hypoglycaemia 11.1-12.3%.	52-week double-blind, parallel- group, randomized clinical trial
N=1098 on Metformin therapy. HbA1c 8.1% (Nauck et al. 2014)	Dulaglutide 0,75 mg and Dulaglutide 1,5 mg	Sitagliptin 100 mg or placebo	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.10% and -0.87% with Dulaglutide 1.5 mg and 0.75 mg. Reduction of body weight by -3.03 kg at 1.5 mg and -2.60 kg with 0.75 mg Dulaglutide. Decrease in LDL after administration of Dulaglutide 1.5 mg. Systolic and diastolic pressure decreased by -1.7 and -0.4 mmHg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 13-17%, diarrhoea 9–13% and vomiting 7-12%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: mild hypoglycaemia: 5.3-10.2%. Investigations: increased amylase and lipase.	52-week randomized, multicenter, double-blind parallel-arm clinical trial
N=424 on therapy with SGLT2 inhibitor with/without Metformin, HbA1c ≥7.0% and ≤9.5% (Ludvik et al. 2018)	Dulaglutide 1.5 mg and Dulaglutide 0.75 mg once a week	Placebo once a week	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by - 1.34% and -1.21% with 1.5 and 0.75 mg Dulaglutide. Reduction of body weight by - 3.1 kg and - 2,6 kg. The decrease in systolic pressure was greater in patients in the Dulaglutide 1.5 mg group by -4.5 mm Hg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea- 15% with 1.5 mg vs 5% with 0.75 mg Dulaglutide, diarrhoea 6% vs 10% and vomiting 4% vs 3% more common with Dulaglutide than with placebo. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: one case of severe hypoglycaemia with 0.75 mg Dulaglutide, mild hypoglycemia - 4%.	24-week randomized, double- blind, placebo- controlled, parallel- arm clinical trial
N=868 inadequately controlled with Metformin. HbA1c 7.0% -10.5% (Ji et al. 2021)	Semaglutide 0,5 mg and Semaglutide 1,0 mg once a week	Sitagliptin 100 mg once a day	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by - 1.4% with 0.5 mg Semaglutide, -1.7% with 1.0 mg Semaglutide. Weight reduction by -2.9 kg with 0.5 mg, and - 4,2 kg with 1,0 mg Semaglutide.	Gastrointestinal disorders: diarrhoea 16.9 – 20.2%, nausea 7.7 – 13.4%, vomiting 4.9 – 6.6%. Eye disorders: diabetic retinopathy complications 5.2% – 7% with Semaglutide 0.5 mg and 1.0 mg. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: decreased appetite in 8%. Investigations: increased lipase 4.5 – 7.7%.	30-week, randomized, double-blind clinical trial
N= 788 on Metformin therapy. HbA1c 7.0–10.5% (Lingvay et al. 2019)	Semaglutide 1,0 mg once a week	Oral Canagliflozin 300 mg once daily	Mean reduction in HbA1c level by - 1.5%. Reduction of body weight by -5.3 kg. Reduction of systolic and diastolic pressure by -3.5 and -1 mmHg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 23%, diarrhoea 15%, vomiting 13%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: symptomatic hypoglycaemia - 2%. Eye disorders: diabetic retinopathy complications 2%.	52-week, double-blind, parallel-group, phase 3b, randomized, active-controlled clinical trial

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, Weight reduction)	Outcomes safety (Adverse events rated by MedRA SOC)	Study design
N= 308 treated only with diet and exercise or on monotherapy with an oral antidiabetic medicinal product. HbA1c 6.5– 9.5% (Seino et al. 2018)	Once a week subcutaneous Semaglutide (0.5 or 1.0 mg)	Oral Sitagliptin 100 mg once a day.	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by - 1.9% and -2.2% with Semaglutide 0.5 mg and 1.0 mg. Reduction of body by -2.2 and -3.9 kg with 0.5 mg and 1.0 mg Semaglutide. Reduction of total cholesterol, LDL, as well as systolic pressure by -6.01 mmHg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: constipation 14.6% and 11.8% with 0.5 and 1.0 mg Semaglutide, nausea 10.7% and diarrhoea 12.7% and 6.8% and 8.8%. Eye disorders: 2 cases of diabetic retinopathy complications.	30-week, phase IIIa randomized, open-label, parallel- group, active- controlled, multicenter clinical trial
N= 1231 on therapy with Metformin, thiazolidinedione or both. HbA1c 7,0–10,5% (Ahrén et al. 2017)	Subcutaneous Semaglutide 0.5 mg once a week, Semaglutide 1.0 mg once a week	Oral Sitagliptin 100 mg once daily	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -% with 0.5 mg and by -1.6% with 1.0 mg Semaglutide. Reduction of body weight by 4.3 kg with 0.5 mg and by 6,1 kg with 1,0 mg Semaglutide.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 18% with 0.5 mg Semaglutide, 18%, with 1.0 mg Semaglutide, diarrhoea - 13% with 0.5 mg and 13% with 1.0 mg Semaglutide. 3 cases of acute pancreatitis were reported with 0.5 mg Semaglutide. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: hypoglycaemia <1% Eye disorders: 1 case of diabetic retinopathy complication.	56-week, phase 3a, randomised, double-blind, actively controlled, parallel-group, multinational, multicentre clinical trial
N= 1089 with poor glycemic control with Metformin (with or without sulfonylurea products). HbA1c 7,0% – 10,0% (Aroda et al. 2017)	Subcutaneous Semaglutide 0.5 mg or 1.0 mg once a week	Once a day Insulin glargine (initial dose 10 IU per day)	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.21% and -1.64%, with 0.5 and 1.0 mg Semaglutide. Weight reduction by -3.47 kg and - 5.17 kg with 0.5 and 1.0 Semaglutide. Systolic pressure decreases by -5.17 mmHg with 1.0 mg Semaglutide.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 21% with 0.5 mg and 22% with 1.0 mg Semaglutide, diarrhoea 16%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: decreased appetite 7%, mild hypoglycaemia 4–6%. Eye disorders: diabetic retinopathy complications - <1%. Investigations: 10% had increased lipase.	30-week, randomized, open-ended, parallel-group, multicenter, multinational, phase 3a clinical trial
N= 388 treated with diet and exercise alone for at least 30 days before screening. HbA1c 7,0%-10,0% (Sorli et al. 2017)	Semaglutide once a week (0.5 mg or 1.0 mg)	Corresponding placebo (0.5 mg or 1.0 mg)	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.45% with 0.5 mg and with -1.55% with 1.0 mg Semaglutide. Reduction of body weight by -3.73 kg with 0.5 mg and by - 4,53 kg with 1,0 mg Semaglutide.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 20% with 0.5 mg and 24% with 1.0 mg Semaglutide, diarrhoea 13% with 0.5 mg and 11% with 1.0 mg Semaglutide, vomiting 4-7%. Investigations: increased amylase and lipase.	30-week, double-blind, randomized, parallel-group, international, placebo-controlled phase 3a clinical trial
N=243 on a diet or exercise or on oral monotherapy with a glucose- lowering medicinal product. HbA1c between 6.5% and 9.5% (Yamada et al. 2020)	Oral Semaglutide (3 mg, 7 mg, or 14 mg)	Placebo or subcutaneous Liraglutide 0.9 mg once a day.	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by - 1.1% with Semaglutide 3 mg, - 1.5% with Semaglutide 7 mg, and -1,7% with Semaglutide 14 mg. Reduction of body weight by 5% with Semaglutide 14 mg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: constipation 10-13% with oral Semaglutide, nausea 4-10%. Infections and infections: nasopharyngitis 16-20%. Eye disorders: 4 cases of diabetic retinopathy complications. Investigations: increased amylase and lipase. One case of thyroid malignancy (Semaglutide 7 mg)	52-week, randomised, double-blind clinical trial
N=731 with poor glycemic control with insulin with or without Metformin. HbA1c 7,0–9,5% (Zinman et al. 2019)	Oral Semaglutide 3 mg (N = 184), 7 mg (N = 182) or 14 mg (N = 181)	Placebo (N = 184)	Mean reduction in HbA1c level by - 0.6%, -0.9% and -1.3% with 3, 7 and 14 mg Semaglutide, respectively. Weight reduction by -0.9 kg, -2.0 kg и - 3.3 kg with 3 mg, 7 and 14 mg Semaglutide.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 11.4% - 23.2, diarrhoea 8.7–14.9%, vomiting 6.0–9.9%. Infections and infections: Nasopharyngitis: 9.9-14.7%.	52-week randomized, double- blind, parallel-group clinical trial
N=822, on Metformin therapy. HbA1c 7,0–10,5% (Rodbard et al. 2019)	Oral Semaglutide 14 mg (n = 412)	Empagliflozin 25 mg (n = 410)	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by - 1.3% with Semaglutide 14 mg. Weight reduction by - 4.7 kg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 19.8%, diarrhoea 9.3%, vomiting 7.3%. Eye disorders: diabetic retinopathy complication was reported by 3.4%.	52-week, randomized multinational, open-label clinical trial
N=324 on therapy with Metformin or sulfonylurea, or both, or basal insulin with or without Metformin in the last 90 days. HbA1c 7,0– 9,5%. Glomerular filtration rate 30–59 mL/min for 1.73 m ² (Mosenzon et al. 2019)	Oral Semaglutide (dose increased up to 14 mg/day)	Placebo	Mean reduction in HbA1c level by - 1.0%. Weight reduction by - 3.7 kg. The mean systolic pressure decreases by -7 mm Hg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 19%, constipation 12%, vomiting 12% - more common with oral Semaglutide than with placebo.	26-week, randomized, double- blind, placebo- controlled, phase 3a clinical trial, conducted in eight countries.
N=703 with poor glycemic control only with diet and exercise. HbA1c 8.0% (Aroda et al. 2019)	Once daily oral Semaglutide 3 mg, 7 mg, 14 mg	Placebo	Mean reduction of HbA1c level with Semaglutide was: - 0,6% [3 mg], -0,9% [7 mg] и -1,1% [14 mg]. Weight reduction with Semaglutide by -0.1 kg [3 mg], -0.9 kg [7 mg] and -2,3 kg [14 mg].	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 8-16.0%, diarrhoea 5.1–8.6%, vomiting 2.9-6.9%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: mild hypoglycaemia between 0.6 – 2.9%. Eye disorders: diabetic retinopathy complication 0.6–1.1%. Investigations: increased lipase.	26-week, phase 3a, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, parallel-group clinical trial

Table 5. PICOS- dual GIP/ GLP-1 receptor agonist.

Population (N)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes efficacy (HbA1c, Weight reduction)	Outcomes safety (Adverse events rated by MedRA SOC)	Study design
N=636, who have discontinued oral glucose-lowering monotherapy or have not been treated so far. HbA1c ≤8.5% or >8.5%. (Inagaki et al. 2022)	Tirzepatide (5, 10 or 15 mg)	Dulaglutide 0.75 mg once a week	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -2.4% with Tirzepatide 5 mg, -2.6% with Tirzepatide 10 mg, -2.8 with Tirzepatide 15 mg. Dose-dependent weight reduction by -5.8 kg with 5 mg, -8.5 kg with 10 mg and -10.7 kg with 15 mg Tirzepatide.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 12% with 5 mg vs 20% with 10 mg vs 20% with 15 mg Tirzepatide, constipation 15% vs 18% vs 14%. Infections and infections: nasopharyngitis 18%, 16% 14%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: no clinically significant hypoglycaemia has been reported.	52-week, double-blind, multicenter, randomized, parallel-group, active-controlled clinical trial
N=478, who have not been on glucose-lowering therapy so far. HbA1c 7,9%. (Rosenstock et al. 2021)	Once a week Tirzepatide (5, 10 or 15 mg)	Placebo	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.87% with Tirzepatide 5 mg, -1.89% with Tirzepatide 10 mg and -2,07% with Tirzepatide 15 mg. Weight reduction by -7.0 kg with Tirzepatide 5 mg, -7.8 kg with Tirzepatide 10 mg and -9.5 kg with Tirzepatide 15 mg. Systolic pressure decreases by -5.2 mmHg with 15 mg Tirzepatide.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 12-18%, diarrhoea 12-14% and vomiting 2-6%. Infections and infections: nasopharyngitis 7%. Nervous system disorders: headache 5%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: no clinically significant or severe hypoglycaemia was reported with Tirzepatide, mild hypoglycemia had <1% of the patients. Investigations: increased amylase and lipase.	40-week, double-blind, randomized, placebo- controlled, parallel-group, multicenter clinical trial
N=1879 on monotherapy with Metformin 1500 mg/day. HbA1c 8.28% (Frias et al. 2021)	Tirzepatide at a dose of 5 mg, 10 mg or 15 mg	Semaglutide at a dose of 1 mg.	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -2,01%, -2,24% and -2,30% with 5 mg, 10 mg and 15 mg Tirzepatide, respectively. Weight reduction by -7,6 kg, -9,3 kg and -11,2 kg respectively with Tirzepatide 5 mg, 10 mg or 15 mg. Systolic and diastolic pressure decreased by -6.5 mm Hg and -2.9 mm Hg with Tirzepatide 15 mg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 17-22%; diarrhoea 13-16%; and vomiting 6-10%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: hypoglycaemia 0.6% (with 5 mg), 0.2% (with 10 mg) and 1.7% (with 15 mg Tirzepatide). Eye disorders: 2 cases of diabetic retinopathy complications.	40-week, parallel-group, randomized, multicenter clinical trial
N=1444 with poor glycemic control with Metformin with or without an SGLT2 inhibitor. HbA1c 7, 0-10,5%. (Ludvik et al. 2021)	Tirzepatide once a week (dose 5, 10 or 15 mg)	Subcutaneous injection of Insulin degludec once a day	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -1.93% with Tirzepatide 5 mg, -2.20% with Tirzepatide 10 mg and -2.37% with Tirzepatide 15 mg. Weight reduction by -7.5, -10.7 and -12.9 kg. Systolic pressure decreases by -5.5 mmHg with Tirzepatide 15 mg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 12-24%, diarrhoea 15-17% and vomiting 6-10% with Tirzepatide. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: decreased appetite 6-12%, hypoglycaemia 1%, 1% and 2% with 5, 10 and 15 mg Tirzepatide. Investigations: No cases of medullary thyroid carcinoma or C- cell hyperplasia have been reported. Eye disorders: three participants had diabetic retinopathy complications.	52-week, open-ended, parallel-group, randomized, multicenter (122 sites), multinational clinical trial
N=475 with poor glycemic control, on Insulin glargine therapy once daily with or without Metformin. HbA1c 8.31%. (Dahl et al. 2022)	Subcutaneous injections of 5 mg, 10 mg or 15 mg Tirzepatide once a week	Placebo	Mean reduction of HbA1c level by -2.11% with Tirzepatide 5 mg, -2.40% with Tirzepatide 10 mg, -2.34% with Tirzepatide 15-mg. Weight reduction by -5.4 kg with 5 mg Tirzepatide, -7.5 kg with 10 mg Tirzepatide, -8.8 kg with 15 mg Tirzepatide. All doses of Tirzepatide were associated with a statistically significant reduction in total cholesterol, LDL, VLDL and triglycerides. The mean change in systolic and diastolic pressure is -6.1 to -12.6 mm Hg and -2.0 to -4.5 mm Hg.	Gastrointestinal disorders: diarrhoea 12%-21%, nausea 13%-18%, vomiting 7-13%. Metabolism and nutrition disorders: decreased appetite 7-14%, hypoglycaemia between 14.2% and 19.3%.	40-week randomized, double-blind, parallel-group, multicenter, placebo- controlled clinical trial.

The most common adverse events were gastrointestinal disorders - nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea, decreased appetite. Followed by nervous system disorders - headache, as well as infections and infestations - nasopharyngitis. During therapy with Exenatide and Lixisenatide, the presence of antibodies is observed, which does not affect glycemic control. Local injection site reactions are more common with Exenatide compared to Lixisenatide.

Human GLP-1 analogues are presented in 26 clinical trials, of which 8 are placebo, 13 are active - controlled and 5 are placebo - and active - controlled. The 26 clinical

trials analyzed were between 24-78 weeks in duration, all randomized controlled. The most commonly used trial design was a parallel-group design. The total number of patients was 18 849, of which 4178 were on Liraglutide therapy, 1663 on Insulin degludec/ Liraglutide combination product therapy (Ideg/Lira), 5513 on Dulaglutide therapy, 4672 on s.c. Semaglutide therapy and 2823 on p.o. Semaglutide therapy. Interventions administered were Liraglutide 1.2 or 1.8 mg once daily alone or in combination with Metformin 1000 mg, Rosiglitazone 4 mg twice daily and Glimepiride 2-4 mg/day. The other interven-

Table 6. Adverse event types and number of clinical trials in which they were reported.0

INN	System-organ class	Subgroup	Number of clinical trials reported
Exenatide	Gastrointestinal disorders	Nausea	10
		Vomiting	6
		diarrhoea	6
	General disorders and administration site conditions	injection site reactions	5
	Metabolism and nutrition disorders	mild hypoglycaemia	10
		decreased appetite	2
	Nervous system disorders	headache	4
	Infections and Infections	nasopharyngitis	4
		upper respiratory tract infections	1
	Lixisenatide	Gastrointestinal disorders	nausea
vomiting			4
diarrhoea			4
Metabolism and nutrition disorders		mild to moderate hypoglycaemia	5
Infections and Infections		nasopharyngitis	1
Liraglutide	Gastrointestinal disorders	nausea	7
		vomiting	7
		diarrhoea	6
		acute pancreatitis	2
	Metabolism and nutrition disorders	mild hypoglycaemia	7
	Nervous system disorders	headache	1
	Infections and Infections	nasopharyngitis	1
Dulaglutide	Gastrointestinal disorders	nausea	8
		vomiting	6
		diarrhoea	7
		constipation	1
		acute pancreatitis	1
		increased amylase and lipase	5
	Investigations	nasopharyngitis	4
	Infections and Infections	nasopharyngitis	4
	Metabolism and nutrition disorders	mild to moderate hypoglycaemia	8
	Semaglutide	Gastrointestinal disorders	nausea
vomiting			7
diarrhoea			9
constipation			3
acute pancreatitis			1
Investigations		increased amylase and lipase	5
Metabolism and nutrition disorders		mild to moderate hypoglycaemia	6
Eye disorders		diabetic retinopathy complications	8
Infections and Infections		nasopharyngitis	2
Tirzepatide	Gastrointestinal disorders	nausea	5
		vomiting	4
		diarrhoea	4
		constipation	1
	Investigations	increased amylase and lipase	1
	Metabolism and nutrition disorders	mild to moderate hypoglycaemia	5
		decreased appetite	2
	Infections and Infections	nasopharyngitis	2
		Eye disorders	diabetic retinopathy complications

tion administered was Dulaglutide 1.5 and 0.75 mg alone. Semaglutide 0.5 mg and 1.0 mg s.c. once weekly and Semaglutide 3 mg, 7 mg or 14 mg p.o. were administered alone. In two trials, Liraglutide 1.2 or 1.8 mg was compared with placebo. In the active-controlled trials, Liraglutide was compared with Glimepiride 8 mg, Exenatide 10 µg, and the combination medicinal product IdegLira was compared with Insulin glargine once daily and with Liraglutide 1.8 mg. Two of the trials were placebo and active-controlled in which Liraglutide was compared with placebo and with Glimepiride 4 mg and Rosiglitazone 4 mg.

Dulaglutide 1.5 and 0.75 mg was compared with placebo in two clinical trials. In the 4 active-controlled trials it was compared with Glimepiride 3 mg, with Insulin glargine and with Metformin 2000 mg/day. 2 of the trials

were placebo and active - controlled and in these Dulaglutide 1.5 and 0.75 mg was compared with placebo and with Exenatide 10 µg and with Sitagliptin 100 mg.

Semaglutide 0.5 mg and 1.0 mg administered subcutaneously was compared with placebo in one clinical trial. In 5 active - controlled clinical trials, Semaglutide was compared 3 times with Sitagliptin 100 mg and once with Canagliflozin 300 mg and with Insulin glargine. Oral Semaglutide (3 mg, 7 mg or 14 mg) was tested versus placebo in three clinical trials and in two active-controlled was compared with Liraglutide 0.9 mg and with Empagliflozin 25 mg.

HbA1c is significantly reduced with Semaglutide 1.0 mg subcutaneously by 1.70%, followed by Semaglutide 14 mg by 1.26%, and with Dulaglutide 1.5 mg and

Liraglutide 1.8 mg by 1.15% and 1.14%, respectively. Body weight reduction is most significant in Semaglutide 1.0 mg by 4.86 kg, followed by Semaglutide 14 mg by 3.5 kg, Liraglutide 1, 8 mg by 2.57 kg and in Dulaglutide 1.5 mg by 2.32 kg. Gastrointestinal disorders are nausea - most common in Liraglutide, vomiting, diarrhoea - in Liraglutide and Semaglutide s.c. Infections and infestations - nasopharyngitis is most commonly seen when taking p.o Semaglutide. An increase in the pancreatic enzymes amylase and lipase is characteristic with the administration of Dulaglutide and Semaglutide. Eye disorders - a diabetic retinopathy complication has been observed after administration of s.c. and of p.o. Semaglutide.

The dual GIP/GLP-1 receptor agonist Tirzepatide is presented in 5 clinical trials, of which 2 were placebo-controlled and 3 were active-controlled. The trials analyzed were between 40–52 weeks in duration, all were randomised controlled, the design used in all five trials was parallel- group. The total number of patients in the trials was 4912. The intervention administered was Tirzepatide 5, 10 or 15 mg. The investigational product was compared with Dulaglutide 0.75 mg, with Semaglutide 1 mg and with Insulin degludec. HbA1c decreased more significantly with Tirzepatide 15 mg - 2.37%, followed by Tirzepatide 10 mg - 2.26% and Tirzepatide 5 mg - 2.06%. Body weight reduction is most significant with Tirzepatide 15 mg - 10.62 kg, followed by Tirzepatide 10 mg - 8.76 kg and Tirzepatide 5 mg - 6.66 kg.

The most common adverse events with Tirzepatide are mild to moderate and transient gastrointestinal disorders - nausea, diarrhoea, vomiting, constipation, and decreased appetite. Some patients had infections and infestations - nasopharyngitis and nervous system disorders - headache. No clinically significant or severe hypoglycemia was reported with Tirzepatide. Eye disorders - diabetic retinopathy complications were reported in 2 of the trials analyzed. Increases in the pancreatic enzymes amylase and lipase were observed in 1 trial. Decreases in systolic and diastolic blood pressure occurred after Tirzepatide administration by up to 12.6 mm Hg for systolic and 4.5 mm Hg for diastolic.

The assessment of the primary efficacy end points based on PICOS is presented graphically in Fig. 2.

The pooled results of the PICO analysis show that the most significant decrease in HbA1c is after Tirzepatide administration - 2.06% (5 mg), 2.26% (10 mg) and 2.37% (15 mg). A mean decrease is observed after administration of Semaglutide 1 mg by 1.70%. The lowest change in HbA1c level is after administration of Exenatide 10 µg (0.83%), Lixisenatide 20 µg (1%) and Semaglutide 3 mg (0.73%).

The reduction in body weight after administration of Tirzepatide at a dose of 5, 10 and 15 mg is by 6.66 kg, by 8.76 kg and by 10.62 kg, respectively, and after administration of Semaglutide 1.0 mg is by 4.86 kg and after administration of oral Semaglutide 14 mg is 3.5 kg. The lowest reduction is after administration of the oral form of Semaglutide 3 mg.

Discussion

Diabetes is still recognized as one of the biggest global burdens both for healthcare systems and society. Patients with diabetes type 2 experienced more macrovascular complications than patients with diabetes type 1 (84% vs. 41%). Hypertension was the most frequent complication; it was observed in 87% of the patients with diabetes type 2. (Dimitrova et al. 2015).

Patients prescribed newer antidiabetic medicinal products need support, wider awareness about side effects, contraindications, and methods to solve problems concerning complications, application, and dosage, without always having to consult their physician (Peneva et al. 2024).

The necessity of individual approach in the selection of therapeutic strategy for the patients with diabetes is a priority as the St Vincent declaration assumed, underlying that it has to improve the quality of life of people with diabetes and to promote the education of patients to prevent diabetes complications (Petkova et al. 2011).

Liutkus et al. compare administration of Exenatide twice-daily versus placebo in 165 patients who were sub-optimally controlled on thiazolidinedione with or without Metformin. It is found that Exenatide added to thiazolidinedione alone or in combination with Metformin significantly improves glycemic control. The most common adverse events (Exenatide versus placebo) are gastrointestinal disorders: nausea (12% versus 2%), vomiting (8% versus 0%) and headache (4% versus 4%) (Liutkus et al. 2010).

To simplify the once-weekly administration of Exenatide, its microspheres have been reformulated into a ready-to-use autoinjector with Miglyol diluent (Exenatide QWS-AI). Wysham et al. compare the efficacy and safety of Exenatide QWS-AI to the first-in-class Exenatide administered twice daily (BID). Patients were randomized to Exenatide QWS-AI (2 mg) or Exenatide twice daily (10 µg) for 28 weeks. Exenatide QWS-AI is associated with a greater reduction in HbA1c, similar weight loss and a favorable gastrointestinal profile compared with Exenatide administered twice daily. Mild hypoglycemia occurs most commonly with concomitant use with sulfonylureas. Both Exenatide QWS-AI and Exenatide BID reduce systolic blood pressure by 0.8 ± 1.1 mm Hg and -1.6 ± 1.4 mm Hg, respectively (Wysham et al. 2018).

Rosenstock et al. compare the efficacy and safety of Lixisenatide administered once daily versus Exenatide twice daily in type 2 diabetes inadequately controlled with Metformin. Lixisenatide administered once daily demonstrated non-inferior reduction in HbA1c levels, with slightly lower mean weight reduction, lower incidence of hypoglycemia and better gastrointestinal tolerability compared with Exenatide administered twice daily. In the Lixisenatide group, fewer participants experienced symptomatic hypoglycemia (2.5% vs. 7.9% Exenatide), with fewer gastrointestinal disorders (nausea: 24.5% vs. 35.1% - Exenatide). The mean decrease in systolic pressure is -2.9 mmHg in the Lixisenatide group and -2.5 mmHg in the Exenatide group; for diastolic pressure, the mean decreases are -1.8 mmHg and -1.3 mmHg, respectively (Rosenstock et al. 2013).

Nauck et al. evaluated the efficacy and safety of adding Liraglutide to Metformin versus adding placebo or Glimpiride to Metformin in patients previously treated with oral glucose-lowering therapy. They found that Liraglutide administered once daily reduces body weight and is associated with lower incidence of hypoglycemia compared with Glimpiride. The incidence of mild hypoglycemia with Liraglutide (3%) is comparable to that with placebo and lower than that with Glimpiride (17%). Nausea is reported by 11–19% of patients treated with Liraglutide. A decrease in systolic blood pressure of 2–3 mmHg is observed at the end of the trial in patients on and 1.8 mg Liraglutide therapy (Nauck et al. 2008).

Ludvik et al. evaluates the safety and efficacy of adding Dulaglutide once weekly to the current treatment regimen in patients whose diabetes is inadequately controlled with SGLT2 inhibitors, with or without Metformin. The primary objective is to test the superiority of Dulaglutide (1.5 mg or 0.75 mg) versus placebo on the change in HbA1c level from baseline. Dulaglutide results in significant and clinically meaningful improvements in glycemic control. Gastrointestinal disorders: nausea 15% in the Dulaglutide 1.5 mg group vs 5% in the Dulaglutide 0.75 mg group, diarrhoea 6% vs 10% and vomiting 4% vs 3%. The decrease in systolic blood pressure is greater in patients in the Dulaglutide 1.5 mg group by - 4.5 mm Hg, respectively (Ludvik et al. 2018).

The Seino team evaluates the safety and efficacy of monotherapy with Semaglutide 0.5 and 1.0 mg administered subcutaneously once weekly versus Sitagliptin in Japanese patients with type 2 diabetes. Semaglutide significantly reduces HbA1c levels and body weight compared with Sitagliptin. Mean HbA1c level decreases by 1.9% and 2.2% with Semaglutide 0.5 and 1.0 mg versus 0.7% with Sitagliptin. After administration of Semaglutide, there is a reduction in total cholesterol and LDL as well as systolic blood pressure by - 6.01 mmHg (Seino et al. 2018).

The Mosenzon team examines the efficacy and safety of oral Semaglutide 14 mg in patients with type 2 diabetes and moderate renal impairment. Participants were randomly assigned to receive oral Semaglutide or corresponding placebo for 26 weeks, in addition to baseline therapy. Oral Semaglutide is efficacious in patients with type 2 diabetes and moderate renal impairment, potentially providing a new treatment option for this patient population. Safety, including renal safety, is consistent with the class of GLP-1 receptor agonists. Gastrointestinal disorders, mainly mild to moderate nausea, are more common with oral Semaglutide than with placebo. Mean systolic blood pressure decreases by an average of -7 mm Hg after Semaglutide administration (Mosenzon et al. 2019).

Rosenstock et al. aims to evaluate the efficacy, safety and tolerability of Tirzepatide as monotherapy versus placebo in patients with type 2 diabetes inadequately controlled with diet and exercise alone. At week 40, all doses of Tirzepatide are superior to placebo in terms of changes from baseline in HbA1c level, fasting serum glucose and body weight reduction. More participants on Tirzepatide therapy than placebo achieve a target HbA1c value below

7.0%. The most common adverse events with Tirzepatide are mild to moderate gastrointestinal disorders: nausea, diarrhoea and vomiting. No clinically significant or severe hypoglycemia has been reported with Tirzepatide. Tirzepatide causes dose-dependent body weight reduction ranging from 7.0 to 9.5 kg. Systolic blood pressure decreases by -5.2 mmHg with Tirzepatide 15 mg. (Rosenstock et al. 2021).

Regarding the incidence of hypoglycemia during clinical trials - the highest risk of hypoglycemia is after the administration of Exenatide and it increases with combination therapy with sulfonylureas. Very common gastrointestinal disorders are nausea, vomiting and diarrhoea. The incidence of nausea is the highest after administration of Exenatide, Liraglutide and Lixisenatide. There are reported cases of acute pancreatitis for all representatives of GLP-1 receptor agonists, but the incidence is low - up to 0.4%. Infections and infestations - nasopharyngitis is more commonly reported by patients taking p.o. Semaglutide. Increased pancreatic enzymes amylase and lipase are reported following administration of Dulaglutide, Semaglutide and Tirzepatide. Eye disorders: cases of diabetic retinopathy complications are reported following administration of Semaglutide and Tirzepatide. Patients may form antibodies to certain GLP-1 receptor agonists that could affect their efficacy, especially Exenatide and Lixisenatide. This immunogenicity may lead to general disorders and administration site conditions - injection site reactions and potential anaphylaxis. The long-term effects on the thyroid gland with the use of GLP-1 agonists are under investigation. Liraglutide stimulates calcitonin release in rodent models, leading to C-cell hyperplasia and thyroid tumors. Effects on humans remain unclear, with further research needed. Therefore, GLP-1 agonists are not recommended to be used in patients with a personal or family history of multiple endocrine neoplasia 2A (MEN 2A), multiple endocrine neoplasia 2B (MEN 2B) or medullary thyroid carcinoma (Collins et al. 2024). Cardiovascular benefits in the analyzed clinical trials demonstrate Liraglutide, Dulaglutide, Semaglutide and Tirzepatide. Following their administration, reductions in systolic and diastolic blood pressure, total cholesterol and LDL are observed. The most significant reductions in systolic and diastolic pressure are demonstrated by Semaglutide and Tirzepatide. And this is an enormous effect as the consequences for the cardiovascular system may be irreversible. This includes: stroke, congestive heart failure, myocardial infarction and cardiovascular death. (Dimitrova et al. 2014)

Conclusion

GLP-1 receptor agonists have a serious superiority over other antidiabetic medicinal products in terms of reducing HbA1c levels and weight reduction without the risk of hypoglycemic episodes. The safety profiles of all representatives of this class are similar. Semaglutide and

Tirzepatide demonstrate the highest efficacy in reducing both HbA1c levels by -2.37% and -1.70% with subcutaneous Semaglutide 1 mg, respectively and body weight by -10.62 kg after administration of Tirzepatide 15 mg and by -4.86 kg with subcutaneous Semaglutide 1 mg, respectively. In clinical trials, GLP - 1 agonists demonstrate

cardiovascular benefits in patients with type 2 diabetes and established risk of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. There is strong evidence to support the use of GLP-1 agonists in overweight or obese patients who have cardiovascular disease, impaired renal function or are at high risk of hypoglycaemia.

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